

NFDI4Earth

Deliverable D1.3.12

Technical specification for single point of access and process model

Initial document

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Executive summary

This deliverable is a specification that outlines the process for managing the life cycle of education and training materials and services, including submitting, reviewing, publishing, revising, versioning, and using them, through a single point of access for the NFDI4Earth project. It starts by introducing the input used to develop the specification, including a comparison of learning management systems and their capabilities. The second part of the specification describes the process model for the life cycle of the open educational resources to be hosted on the platform, including the initial implementation and the long-term vision for the platform. The report also includes an initial version of the metadata specification to make the resources findable and integrate them into the NFDI4Earth knowledge graph.

Abbreviations

D1.3.1 - Deliverable 1.3.1: Mapping of existing educational resources and initial education and training needs within the Earth system science community

D1.3.12 - Deliverable 1.3.12: Technical specification for single point of access and process model (initial document)

ECTS - European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System

EduHubs - An open network of education and training hubs

EduPilots - Educational Pilots

EduTrain - Education and Training Materials and Services, see <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2participate/education-training>

ES - Earth System

ESS - Earth System Sciences

FAIR - Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability

HSBO - Bochum University of Applied Sciences

IEEE - Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers

LMS - Learning Management System

M1.3 - Measure 1.3: Education and Training Materials and Services

NFDI - National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdaten Infrastruktur), see <http://www.nfdi.de>

NFDI4Earth - NFDI Consortium Earth System Sciences / NFDI Konsortium Erdsystemforschung, see <https://www.nfdi4earth.de>

OER - Open Educational Resources

RDM - Research Data Management

TA - Task Area

TUM - Technische Universität München

UNIHH - Universität Hamburg

UNIMS - Universität Münster

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1 Introduction

This deliverable is the first version of a specification that describes (a) how a single point of access is supposed to work for the NFDI4Earth education and training materials and services, and (b) the process of managing the life cycle of these materials and services, including submitting, reviewing, publishing, revising, versioning, and using them. It starts by introducing the input the M1.3 team has used to develop these specifications, including a detailed comparison of existing learning management systems (LMSs) and their capabilities. The second part describes the process model for the life cycle of the Open Educational Resources (OERs) to be hosted, including the underlying assumptions and initial descriptions of the first minimal implementation and the long-term vision for the platform.

2 Input

This section introduces the inputs that the M1.3 team has used to develop this specification and summarizes the main results for the LMS review and Metadata specification.

2.1 NFDI interviews

The M1.3 as a member of the software expert group together with other group members surveyed the work done in the round one NFDI consortia, based on the information available on their websites and emails to contact persons. The purpose of the survey was to collect information about the technical stack employed by previous rounds. The survey was conducted over the summer of 2022. The following questions were used to structure the data collection process:

1. What does the data model look like? Which metadata standards are used as a basis?
2. Which software is used to implement a data search (e.g., a metadata catalog, such as CKAN)?
3. What software is used to implement a search for software (if any)?
4. Is metadata harvesting implemented? If so, based on which schemas and interfaces?
5. How is quality assessment for metadata performed (e.g., review by experts)?
6. On what basis is the knowledge base implemented (MySQL and Maria DB are on the web, is there a Triplestore, for example)?
7. Is a software product used to visualize the data? If yes, which one?

8. Are there HPC components in the architecture? Which functions will be implemented there?
9. Is there a plan to provide educational material? If so, how (e.g., in a separate EduHub/portal)?

The results of this survey concerning educational services revealed a broad range of information. The online education activities conducted at the NFDI consortia at the time of the survey included booklet dissemination e.g., workflows and data formats, publishing training materials under an open license in Zenodo and then publishing them in a web portal, storing material in the knowledge base and videos on YouTube, slides, reading the docs, markdown workbooks and launching podcasts websites. Publishing training materials on Zenodo and videos on YouTube were mentioned most frequently.

2.2 “Alpha release” requirements

The EduTrain team aims to make educational resources readily available through an alpha version website. This website, which could be a Content Management System (CMS), such as the one currently supporting the NFDI4Earth website, must meet the following minimum requirements:

- The EduTrain team should be able to upload educational resources, add richly formatted descriptions, and embed media files, including videos from external resources.
- The educational resources must be annotated by the EduTrain team with metadata to facilitate their discovery through OneStop4All [1].
- The CMS should allow for the categorization of course material in a catalog that users can use to access the material.
- Users should be able to locate the educational resources using a search function and access and download the uploaded material.

Following these requirements, we will review and compare the various tools and metadata that can help achieve these goals.

2.3 Web-based open-source learning management system

From the broad range of learning management systems (LMSs) on the market, we have limited our choice according to the needs of the NFDI4Earth online educational services. Therefore, open and web-based systems for managing educational content were reviewed. From the learning management systems that had these characteristics, the ones that were widely used

for educational and academic purposes were selected, e.g., ILIAS was ruled out given that the majority of its customers are non-academics [2].

A comprehensive comparison of the features of Canvas, Moodle LMS, Open edX, Chamilo, and Sakai, with our requirements for the first version of the NFDI4Earth educational portal, is given in the supplemental table [NFDI4Earth_D1.3.12_EduTrain-portal-requirements.xlsx](#). The table includes the most well-known open-source and web-based learning management systems [3–7].

Among the five learning management systems initially evaluated, Moodle LMS and Open edX emerged as the most compatible with our requirements for the initial version. Based on our comprehensive evaluation, detailed in the table above, the other three platforms did not meet our essential “must” requirements, and hence are not discussed further in this report.

The features of these LMSs may not be the same as what's in the table by the time we are actually going to use them. Likewise some features may change over time or in the near future; we chose these two LMSs because overall, they matched our requirements best. The M1.3 team will try both of these systems for a few months to gain practical experience beyond the systems we already use at our respective institutions to make an informed decision. We also surveyed the 2022 educational pilots for the technical requirements of their final products and added them to the table above. Our goal is to provide the users of the NFDI4Earth with intuitive, modern learning and training experiences, therefore many of the fields in the table will become mandatory in future versions and new requirements may be added.

2.3.1 Open edX

Developed by the edX organization, the web-based open-source platform is used for creating, delivering, and analyzing online courses. The Open edX platform is a Python/Django REST service and has react micro-frontends. It consists of millions of lines of code across approximately 200 repositories written by hundreds of contributors [8].

2.3.2 Moodle

Moodle is an open-source flexible, most widely used learning management system, written in PHP. Moodle is structured as an application core, surrounded by plugins providing numerous functionalities. It has a highly extensible and customizable design without modifying the core libraries. Moodle plugins are PHP script folders and, if necessary, CSS, JavaScript, etc. Copyright is not assigned to a single entity and is owned by individual contributors, although the project is managed by the company Moodle Pty Ltd in Perth Australia, owned by Moodle's founder Martin Dougiamas [9].

2.4 Metadata schema for the NFDI4Earth online training platform

We have used internationally recognized standards including the IEEE Standard for Learning Object Metadata [10], Metadata Schema for Research Data Management Training Materials [11], and Dublin Core Metadata Element Set [12] as foundations to develop the basic metadata fields for the NFDI4Earth training catalog. A few additional fields were incorporated, derived from the need analysis results [1]. Relying on these existing schemas and vocabularies, we envision a re-use of the corresponding terms without the need to establish an NFDI4Earth-specific schema and to increase compatibility with other sources of OERs.

Table 1 provides an overview of the metadata elements for describing the educational material in our e-catalog. A significant portion of the items in this table are borrowed from the IEEE standard, which is recognized as a premier standard for Learning Object Metadata at an international level. In our selection process, we have aimed to strike a balance between the comprehensiveness of metadata information and the required effort to produce them. This ensures the materials are easily findable, allowing users to efficiently filter out materials based on their needs, while the number of mandatory fields does not pose an unnecessary burden on educational content creators.

Our catalog currently includes 17 fields, with 7 of them being mandatory. We selected these mandatory fields after a careful evaluation of the metadata provided by the original publishers of the mapped resources (see D1.3.1) [1].

The final stage of creating metadata objects for NFDI4Earth's educational materials involved aligning the metadata across all products within the project. The living handbook team, OneStop 4All team, and EduTrain team worked together to harmonize the metadata and ensure consistency throughout the project. This ensures consistency in the structure of our metadata and makes it easier for users to search for resources across different products.

It's important to note that the selected fields may be subject to change as we continue to gather feedback from our users and add new resources to our platform.

Table 1: metadata schema for NFDI4Earth training platform [10–12]

Field	Explanation	Vocabulary	Mandatory
Title	Name given to this learning object.	-	Yes
Subject	Specification of the thematic scope covered by the resource.	Subject areas by German Research Foundation [13]	Yes
Description	A textual description of the content of this learning object.	-	Yes
Publisher	An entity responsible for making the resource available.	-	No
Date	The date of the contribution.	-	No

Field	Explanation	Vocabulary	Mandatory
Learning resource type	Specific kind of learning object. The most dominant kind shall be first. Can be expanded by new entries.	Exercise, Slide, Narrative text, Quiz, Video	Yes
Identifier	A globally unique label that identifies this metadata record.	-	No
Source	A related resource from which the described resource is derived.	-	Yes
Language	The human language used by the typical intended user of this learning object. Can be expanded by new entries.	EN, DE	Yes
Rights	Information about rights held in and over the resource.	-	Yes
Requirements	The technical capabilities necessary for using this learning object./Specification of required prior knowledge of the participant.	-	No
Difficulty	How hard it is to work with or through this learning object for the typical intended target audience. Can be expanded by new entries.	Beginner, Intermediate, Advanced	No
Keyword	A keyword or phrase describing the topic Of this learning object. This data element should not be used for characteristics that can be described by other data elements.	-	No
Code	Whether this learning object contains programming lessons or exercises.	Yes, No	No
Contact	Contact details of the person(s) responsible for this resource.	-	No
Logo	The logo, if any, of the publisher responsible for this learning object.	-	No
Dependencies different modules	This category defines the relationship Between this learning object and other Learning objects if any. To define multiple relationships, there May be multiple instances of this Category. If there is more than one target Learning object, then each target shall have a new relationship instance.	-	No

3 Process model

This section describes the lifecycle of education and training materials after their initial development. We discuss the assumptions, the general process stages to be considered, the requirements for the initial implementation, and finally our vision for the mid to long-term realization within the NFDI4Earth service ecosystem.

3.1 Assumptions

The points raised in this section summarise the assumptions about our NFDI4Earth education and training materials and services. They have emerged from discussions among the M1.3 team, our exchange with the larger NFDI4Earth consortium, and related initiatives (see the focus group interview described in D1.3.1 [1], for example), as well as lessons learned in other projects

we have been involved in. The process stages as well as the requirements specification detailed in this report are based on the following assumptions:

1. **Submission of educational materials needs to be as easy as possible.** The academic community has started to acknowledge outputs beyond the traditional article, including the development of software and the provision of datasets. While NFDI4Earth strives to support this cultural change, there do not seem to be sufficient incentives for the development and publication of Open Educational Resources (OERs) yet. Therefore, the process of submitting such materials to us needs to be as easy and frictionless as possible. Any burdens or restrictions for the developers of these materials, such as format conversions, will likely reduce the number of materials submitted.
2. **Platform independence is vital to ensure reuse.** There are currently at least a handful of different learning management systems in use both at German universities and internationally (Section 2.2). While they all offer a similar set of functionalities, interoperability is limited when it comes to migrating larger educational units such as whole courses. As materials provided through NFDI4Earth should be re-usable as easily as possible, they need to be made available in a platform-agnostic way, using open formats whenever possible, so that trainers can integrate them into whatever system their institution uses. This may mean that not all features of a particular learning platform, such as the definition of a course structure, can be used.
3. **Modularity increases re-usability.** Besides the interoperability issues mentioned above, a focus on smaller, self-contained units facilitates a flexible combination of such building blocks to larger educational units. Smaller modules are also more likely to be re-used more frequently in different settings. These can be traditional courses for a certain number of ECTS in degree-granting institutions, training programs focusing on specific skills for post-graduate researchers, or individualized learning approaches where learners put together their own program to acquire a predefined set of new skills.
4. **Materials can be used in different settings.** We do not want to focus on either instructor-led courses or self-training programs or have a specific focus on in-person, online, or hybrid training. Ideally, materials submitted to us should be reusable in different settings, and their description should clarify for which context they have been developed, and where the developer sees potential other use cases.
5. **Modular units need to be contextualized.** Besides the above-mentioned contextual information on the educational setting that the materials have been developed for, they also need to be framed when it comes to learning progressions. Prerequisites and outcomes of a specific module need to be explicitly stated so that sets of modules can be chained together in a meaningful way. In a fully semantically annotated set of training materials in the NFDI4Earth knowledge graph, this chaining of smaller blocks to larger

units should be possible automatically. We will keep this vision in mind for the long-term development of the training portal.

6. **Quality control needs to be handled by the community.** We do not foresee a large number of submissions of EduTrain materials in the initial phase of NFDI4Earth beyond the ones produced by our EduPilots and the M1.3 team itself. Therefore, the quality control/reviewing process will be handled by the M1.3 team until we see an increase in submissions. Due to the lack of incentives for the publication of OERs (see above), we currently assume that large numbers of submissions can only be expected in collaboration with conferences and other similar settings, where we request tutorials as part of the submission and the review will therefore be handled by the corresponding program committee. In the long term, we should also discuss to what extent this task can be considered part of EduHubs' responsibilities.
7. **Innovative materials and training approaches may depend on specific technical services.** While we intend to keep our OERs as interoperable and platform-agnostic as possible, we have seen a remarkable increase in the uptake of innovative and effective learning and teaching approaches that do require specific technical setups, most notably in the form of notebooks (e.g., in Jupyter, Google Colab, Quarto, or RStudio). The first set of EduPilots that have been funded in 2022 already shows that notebooks play a vital role for EduTrain and therefore need to be supported as part of the platform. We expect that other new forms of technical tools supporting the training process will evolve during the NFDI4Earth funding period and that our setup needs to be flexible enough to accommodate such developments; otherwise, our offerings will be outdated quickly and not be used.
8. **A centralized approach will not work.** NFDI4Earth will provide its own EduTrain portal where the materials developed by the NFDI4Earth community (e.g., through the EduPilots) will be hosted and the metadata for reviewed relevant externally hosted materials will be made searchable. Nonetheless, we are fully aware that this will be just one portal among many others that provide OERs, even when focusing just on ESS. It is therefore unlikely that any user – especially if they are not aware of NFDI4Earth in the first place – will come to our portal as a starting point. Instead, our materials will mostly be discovered through a plain Web search. It is therefore vital that our materials are presented and annotated in a way that is optimized for discoverability by Web crawlers and that all content is publicly accessible without requirements for logins. Moreover, reuse can further be increased if we allow others to host copies of our materials, using an attribution license (such as CC-BY); however, this needs to be coordinated with the developers of the materials, who own the copyright.

3.2 Process stages

Figure Fig. 1 shows the simplest version of a submission process of materials to the NFDI4Earth training platform that will be implemented for the initial version. The goal is to have a setup running quickly that has as few technical requirements or dependencies as possible, yet still allows us to (a) put materials online for download, and (b) make them findable.

Figure 1: Workflow for the initial implementation

The shown steps are briefly detailed in the following:

1. There are no restrictions as to who can participate in the preparation of materials; however, we are aware that our OERs will typically be provided by teachers in ESS who teach aspects related to research data management (RDM) or data science approaches. These teachers can prepare their materials in any format they see fit, ranging from slides through recorded lectures, podcasts, and exercises (ideally with data or on open datasets), to notebooks and code.
2. In the initial version, submission of materials will be handled through a functional mailbox (e.g., edutrain@nfdi4earth.de; currently under discussion with the TU Dresden team) with forwarding to the M1.3 team members. This setup minimizes the requirements for the

portal and also maximizes the flexibility for OER developers, as they can choose to deliver their materials however they want; anything from Email-attachments, linked files in cloud storage, code repositories, or materials already published on other platforms works. The M1.3 team will then coordinate to decide who will handle that case, communicate with the developer, and be responsible for the publication of the materials.

3. While we want to keep the requirements for the developers as low as possible, some mandatory metadata needs to be submitted to make sure we can make the materials findable, attribute the developer, and display the correct license, so that legally safe re-use is ensured. The set of required (and optional) metadata is shown in the supplemental table. We acknowledge that submissions may come through various channels, and as such, a range of templates will be provided to facilitate the process. and eventually, a user-friendly submission portal. This portal will allow for a more organized and simple process for submitting materials and providing metadata, resulting in more convenience and efficiency. Instructions for the submission process, including the required metadata, will be posted on: <https://www.nfdi4earth.de/2participate/education-training>.
4. After the submission of materials and metadata, an M1.3 team member will review the submission based on the quality control criteria listed in section 3.3. The M1.3 team will ensure that someone with the appropriate background will be assigned the review, both in terms of discipline and career level concerning the target group of the materials.
5. If the submitted materials meet the criteria, they will be published on the portal. Initially, this will be a simple website where the materials can be downloaded (see Section 2.2.3). Metadata will be converted to RDF and submitted to the knowledge graph driving the NFDI4Earth OneStop4All, including links to the actual materials.
6. If the submitted materials or the corresponding metadata do not meet the criteria, the reviewer will contact the developer of the materials and provide feedback explaining what should be fixed for the materials to meet the NFDI4Earth EduTrain criteria. The reviewer shall support the developer in the revision process and make sure that this case is handled by the same person until the materials can be successfully published. The remaining M1.3 team shall support the reviewer in this task.
7. After the publication of materials, the reviewer shall notify and thank the developer for their contribution.

3.3 Quality control criteria for submitted materials

1. Only staff of academic or research institutions will be able to submit training material.
2. Mandatory metadata have to be filled in and, as far as they can be checked by the reviewer, correct.

3. The chosen license has to permit re-use and re-publication.
4. The materials must not contain any materials infringing other parties' copyrights, as far as this can be checked by the reviewer.
5. The materials need to be self-contained with a clear goal explaining what skills learners will acquire by going through the respective unit.
6. Prerequisites need to be clear. This concerns both the knowledge learners need to have before starting the corresponding unit and technical requirements such as access to specific software or data that is not part of the materials.
7. The reviewer has to be able to successfully complete the unit. The interpretation of this step depends to a large extent on the kind of material provided; a set of slides or a video lecture need to be understood by the reviewer, whereas any practical units need to be completed by following the described steps.

3.4 Initial implementation

For the initial implementation, the requirements have deliberately been kept at a minimum. We have tried to get as far as possible with those parts of the NFDI4Earth infrastructure that are already in place.

For the submission of new OERs, we need a functional mailbox with forwarding to the M1.3 team members' email addresses. Accepted OERs need to be published online; this can initially happen on the NFDI4Earth website, or on the NFDI4Earth SharePoint (if public folders can be set up there). Depending on the state of the NFDI4Earth OneStop4All, we need a way to add the OERs' metadata to the knowledge graph, so that the EduTrain materials can be listed, searched, and retrieved.

3.5 Long-term vision

The initial implementation outlined above meets the minimum requirements that will allow us to put the first OERs online. There are a number of process steps and the corresponding technical prerequisites missing that will be elaborated in a revision of this deliverable; however, we already want to give a first overview of the steps and tools we envision for the future of NFDI4Earth EduTrain.

A web-based solution that offers a simple drag-and-drop upload in combination with a metadata editor should be offered for the submission process. The review process should be handled within this tool, and the metadata editor should be connected to the NFDI4Earth knowledge graph to ensure that the correct concepts are used to describe the topic areas

covered, to link to the corresponding providers and their institutions, and to enable direct ingestion of the metadata into the OneStop4All. Accepted materials should then be offered for download in different formats by an automatic conversion tool (e.g., slides uploaded in PowerPoint format as PDF, or videos in different encodings and qualities). Automatic conversion simplifies both the upload- and the download process, putting the OER developer into a position where they can use whatever format they prefer, and allowing users to download them in their preferred formats. Obviously, this only works if the materials are not tied to a specific tool, such as notebooks, which usually cannot be easily converted from one tool to another.

Looking at the overall lifecycle of an OER module, we also need to support revisions, issue tracking, bug fixing, and versioning to ensure that an OER module is not produced once and then slowly dies as it becomes outdated. We should support and encourage continuous updates of the materials, possibly collaboratively, as materials get used and adopted by a larger number of teachers across the community. As much of this functionality resembles the processes used and established in software engineering teams, we have already discussed the role that a platform such as GitHub or GitLab could play in this process; however, this would imply substantial expectations for the OER developers' technical capabilities and might therefore reduce the number of submissions. The process hence needs to strike a balance between the capabilities of the technical tools we employ, and simplicity, especially for contributors not familiar with software versioning tools.

Generally, interactive learning and teaching tools should be enabled with direct access to the NFDI4Earth services and data sources, as these should – in the long run – be the focus of our attention for the education and training activities. Besides the technical platforms required to enable this – e.g., running a notebook server – it also requires integration with a single-sign-on solution for the NFDI4Earth services to authorize access to data and compute services once we reach more specialized pieces of training tied to specific NFDI4Earth components and data. Finally, this login will also be needed to track progress and issue certificates in a self-learning setting (supplemental table).

4 Conclusions

In this initial version of the technical specification for single point of access and process model, we have detailed the requirements to implement the workflows for the planned NFDI4Earth education and training materials and services. We distinguish between the basic requirements of a first minimum viable product that makes our materials findable and downloadable, and the first specifications for the long-term implementation offering a wide range of more advanced features both for the management and for the use of EduTrain materials and services. We have also included a detailed comparison of existing Learning Management Systems relating them to

our functional requirements, as well as an initial version of the metadata specification to make our resources findable and to integrate them with the NFDI4Earth knowledge graph.

The next steps for the M1.3 team will be to test some of the best-fitting candidates for the LMS, including real materials, and go through the workflow of publishing them. Therefore, this report will be updated with more detailed specifications based on the lessons learned and the state of the other NFDI4Earth infrastructure components in 2024.

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